

WP4 ‘Insects in animal feed’: structure, aims and preliminary results of digestibility trials

L. Gasco¹, E.-J. Lock², S. Chatzifotis³, A. Jansman⁴, A. Schiavone⁵, T. Veldkamp⁴

¹University of Turin, largo P. Braccini 2, 10095, Italy, ²Institute of Marine Research, P.O. Box 1870 Nordnes, 5817 Bergen, Norway, ³Hellenic Centre for Marine Research. , PO BOX 2214, 71003 Heraklion, Greece, ⁴Wageningen Livestock Research, De Elst 1, 6708 WD Wageningen, the Netherlands, ⁵University of Turin, largo P. Braccini 2, 10095, Italy; laura.gasco@unito.it

The objective of WP4 “Insects in animal feed” is to validate the inclusion of insect derived proteins in animal diets, ensuring optimal growth, quality and animal health of fish, poultry and piglets on commercially relevant scale. The WP is divided into three different tasks.

In the first task digestibility trials are carried out to assess commercial black soldier fly (BSF) meals produced within one year. The aim is to highlight fluctuation on the meals composition as this could also influence digestibility parameters. Trials are performed both *in vivo*, and *in vitro*. Digestibility trials are also performed assessing three BSF meals produced under different methodologies in WP3 ‘Insect processing’.

The second task aims to evaluate, under farm conditions, the effects of the inclusion of BSF meal in commercial feed formulae for fish (rainbow trout, sea bass and Atlantic salmon), poultry (broiler chickens and laying hens), and weaning piglets.

Finally, the third task aims to validate the impact of diets containing insect derived proteins on product quality and animal health. Physical, chemical and organoleptic quality of animal-derived products (fish meat, broiler meat, and laying hen eggs) are assessed on samples following the large-scale trial. Moreover, physiological effects are evaluated by hematic, biochemical, histological and immuno-histochemical analyses and by metagenomics approach.

The final objective is to validate on commercially relevant scale (TRL 6) research the inclusion of insect-derived proteins in animal diets and to provide the market with commercial feed formulae able to guarantee optimal animal growth and health, and product quality.

After a brief overview of the WP4 structure and aims, the presentation reports the first results obtained in the *in vivo* and *in vitro* digestibility trials on rainbow trout, seabass, Atlantic salmon, broiler chickens and weaning piglets.